

National Action Plans

WP2: Capturing grassroots needs and identifying available solutions

D 2.4: Development of National Action Plans

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Table of content

Document Information	1
Document history	2
Abbreviations	3
Participants	4
Document summary	5
<i>Executive Summary</i>	5
Document content	6
<i>Part. 1 Introduction</i>	6
<i>Part. 2 NAP Country crop focus</i>	6
<i>Part. 3 Country NAP</i>	7
3.1 UK NAP.....	7
3.1.1 Background & Needs.....	7
3.1.2 Crop selection for the UK.....	7
3.1.3 Solutions for the UK.....	7
3.1.4 Conclusions for the UK.....	10
3.2 France NAP.....	11
3.2.1 Background and Needs	11
3.2.2 Crop selection for France.....	11
3.2.3 Solutions for France	11
3.2.4 Conclusions for France.....	14
3.3 Italy NAP	14
3.3.1 Background and Needs	14
3.3.2 Crop selection for Italy.....	15
3.3.3 Solutions for Italy	15
3.3.4 Conclusions for Italy	17
3.4 Greece NAP.....	17
3.4.1 Background and Needs	18
3.4.2 Crop selection for Greece.....	18
3.4.3 Solutions for Greece	18
3.4.4 Conclusions for Greece.....	20
3.5 Latvia NAP.....	21
3.5.1 Background and Needs	21
3.5.2 Crop selection for Latvia	21
3.5.3 Solutions for Latvia.....	21
3.5.4 Conclusions for Latvia	25
3.6 Sweden NAP	25
3.6.1 Background and Needs	25
3.6.2 Crop selection for Sweden.....	25
3.6.3 Solutions for Sweden	25
3.6.4 Conclusions for Sweden	27
3.7 Spain NAP	27
3.7.1 Background and Needs	27
3.7.2 Crop selection for Spain.....	28
3.7.3 Solutions for Spain	28
3.7.4 Conclusions for Spain	30

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TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

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TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

NAP	NATIONAL ACTION PLAN	AHDB	AGRICULTURAL & HORTICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT BOARD
NN	NATIONAL NETWORK	SFI	SUSTAINABLE FARMING INCENTIVE
IWM	INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT	RDP	RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME
NNO	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR	LCA	LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT
OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP	GNSS	GLOBAL NAVIGATION SATELITE SYSTEM
VCS	VEGETABLE CONSULTANCY SERVICES	GHG	GREENHOUSE GAS

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

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TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

This document outlines the first stage of the National Action Plans (NAP) for each participating country and is project deliverable D2.4. It contains an introduction to this first stage of the NAP formulation (Part 1) and highlights the crop focus for each country (Part 2). The main body of the report (Part 3) takes each country individually outlining a specific NAP tailored to that country. Conclusions for this deliverable are presented in Part 4.

Executive Summary

The first draft of a country specific National Action Plan has been developed and presented by matching the expressed needs of stakeholders from the output of the national surveys and focus groups (D2.1) with the technical solutions identified in D2.2.

Countries have selected up to three crops to focus on, which were either identified from their specific Operational Group (OG) or from being the main crop that survey participants were growing for that country. For France only vineyards have been evaluated in the NAP as this was the OG and the crop that 96% of the survey respondents were growing. Other countries had two to three main crops.

It is important to consider that for some countries there are very large regional differences that may include climatic variation, soil type and predominant cropping systems. This would be the case for Italy, Spain and Greece in particular. For the purposes of this draft NAP, we have not ventured into regional differences within a country, but that can be included in the next phase of NAP development in WP3.

Initially, 10-20 solutions have been identified for each country, taken from D2.1 and D2.2 and these will be evaluated and prioritized with the assistance of the National Experts within the National workshops in T3.1. Solutions are very diverse between countries but alternative weeding techniques such as different forms of mechanical weeding, precision or spot spraying, robots, thermal weeding, living mulches, cover crops and cultural options such as cultivar choice and crop rotations are all key solutions. Along with these technical solutions the NAP includes policy-based solutions that will require implementation to ensure the best uptake of Integrated weed management (IWM).

This information is critical to tailor 'Best Practices' designed to cater to the diverse needs, contexts, and farmer profiles found throughout Europe and the UK, which will be accomplished within the next phase of the project (WP3).

Document content

Part. 1 Introduction

To better understand the potential for farmers to embrace alternative weed control methods and identify the impediments that may obstruct their adoption, we embarked on an extensive online survey (T2.1). The survey aimed to uncover the needs, gaps, and barriers related to alternative weed control practices across Europe and the UK. From its inception, OPER8 has demonstrated a commitment to engaging key stakeholders throughout its journey. The foundation of this endeavour lies in the establishment of national networks (NN) of experts within each participating country, a significant accomplishment within Work Package (T1.1). We leveraged our extensive network, both within and beyond the NN, to ensure the widest possible dissemination of this survey. To delve deeper and to gather essential insights from the bottom-up, the results of each survey conducted within our partner countries underwent rigorous examination and discussion within the respective NN. This collaborative process provided us with a contextual understanding that goes beyond mere statistics.

Simultaneously, we employed a top-down strategy to unearth the technical and practical solutions available for weed control within each participating country (T2.2). This approach allowed us to classify solutions according to the five pillars of the Integrated Weed Management framework².

But OPER8's ambitions extend beyond the realm of practical solutions. We are poised to effect change at the political level as well. Our national action plans propose key infrastructure alterations crucial to encouraging the widespread adoption of alternative weed control methods. These recommendations emerge from data collected through the stakeholder surveys and focus group workshops (T2.1).

National action plans have been developed by matching the expressed needs of stakeholders across regions (D2.1) with the technical solutions identified in D2.2. In the following sections of this report, we will delve into specific focus crops and sectors, identify suitable technical solutions tailored to each, and outline other actions/initiatives that can drive their adoption within the diverse agricultural landscapes of the OPER8 project's partner countries. Initially, up to 15 solutions have been identified for each country and these will be evaluated and prioritized with the assistance of the National Experts within the National workshops in T3.1. This information is critical to tailor 'Best Practices' designed to cater to the diverse needs, contexts, and farmer profiles found throughout Europe, which will be accomplished within WP3.

Part. 2 NAP Country crop focus

The crops selected for the country specific NAP are show in Table 5. The specific crops to focus on in each country have mainly originated from the OG. However, for some countries the OG did not represent the main cropping systems and so the data from the survey respondents (T2.1) has been used to select the most common cropping system.

TABLE 5 THE SELECTED CROPPING SYSTEMS FOR EACH COUNTRY SPECIFIC NAP

	Country						
	UK	France	Italy	Greece	Spain	Latvia	Sweden
Main crop	Cereals	Vineyards	Vineyards	Field vegetables	Horticulture	Field vegetables	Cereals
2 nd crop	Field vegetables	-	Field vegetables	Vineyards/orchards	Vineyards	Arable	Potatoes/Sugar beet
3 rd crop	Grassland	-	Arable crops	Cereals	Cereals	-	Field vegetables

Part. 3 Country NAP

3.1 UK NAP

3.1.1 Background & Needs

The UK agricultural industry has long relied on chemical herbicides as a primary means of weed control. Herbicides offer a convenient and effective way to manage weed populations, saving farmers time and labour. However, this heavy dependence on herbicides has created a cycle of continuous usage, often without adequate rotation or diversification of weed control methods. This overreliance has led to several significant issues relating to herbicide resistance development, limited herbicide options and increased weed pressure. UK farmers were interested in alternative weed control methods, but several specific needs were identified from the surveys (D2.1).

1. Farmers need greater confidence in the efficacy of alternative weed control methods. (This is relevant across all cropping systems and farm management styles across the UK).
2. Farmers need access to alternative weed control equipment.
3. Farmers need affordable alternative solutions for weed control.
4. Alternative solutions need to be more effective than herbicides and less time consuming to implement.
5. Farmers need more information on alternative weed control solutions.

3.1.2 Crop selection for the UK

In the UK the original OGs research was in grassland (electrical weeding) and field scale vegetables (mechanical weeding). However, weed control is far more intensive in arable cropping than grassland in the UK. Of the 44 farmers that completed the survey (D2.1), 77% indicated that cereals and oilseeds were the main crop and 65% of the scientific papers in D2.2 referred to arable crops. To maximise the benefit of this NAP we have therefore chosen to concentrate on arable and horticultural crops in the UK, with grassland as a 3rd crop choice.

3.1.3 Solutions for the UK

As specified in Part 1, 15 solutions have been identified for the UK and are presented in Table 6. We have chosen to break these down into both technical and political solutions based on the feedback from our survey and focus group results (D2.1). These consider the five needs highlighted for the UK with an aim to address those needs.

TABLE 6 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR THE UK NAP

Solutions for the UK		Cropping system		
		Arable	Field vegetables	Grassland
	Technical solutions			
1	Mechanical weeding (including camera guided systems): Requires wider dissemination of information on efficacy, carbon footprint, <i>low</i>	✓	✓	
2	Targeted herbicide application/spot spraying : Demonstration & promotion of kit and of emerging technologies from other countries.	✓	✓	✓
3	Robotics : Demonstration and promotion of available kit and of new emerging technologies from other countries.	✓	✓	✓
4	Bioherbicides : More development from the agrochemical industry, more data to prove efficacy, cost benefit analysis required.	✓	✓	✓

5	Living Mulches (including companion crops): require more data to prove efficacy compared to herbicides	✓	✓	
6	Electrical weeding: requires more available machinery options.	✓	✓	✓
7	Competitive cultivars/enhanced plant breeding	✓	✓	
8	Mulches (non-living/dead mulches)		✓	
9	Cultural control (tillage, crop rotations and inclusion of grass leys, delayed drilling, increased seed rates, false seedbed, hygiene etc etc)	✓	✓	
10	Grazing in rotation: Introduction of livestock into arable or horticultural systems	✓	✓	
11	Laser weeding: Integration with emerging new technologies could aid uptake			✓
12	Flame weeding: cost benefit/ carbon footprint analysis		✓	
Political Solutions				
1	Increase the number of grants for the purchase of equipment.	✓	✓	✓
2	Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	✓	✓	✓
3	Robust independent trial data to quantify the efficacy of alternative methods	✓	✓	✓
4	Grants for trials of alternative methods	✓	✓	✓
5	Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information	✓	✓	✓

3.1.3.1 Technical solutions

Matching of the needs to the practical solutions lead us to identify the practical options for weed control in cereals, outdoor vegetable production and grassland systems (Table 6).

For this first draft of the NAP, technologies have been grouped into short and medium-long term solutions. For the short-term solutions, we recommend carrying out cost/benefit analysis to determine the efficacy, costs, environmental impacts and best practices of the technologies, alongside the data gathered from T2.2 and T2.3. This would refine the information to give a more detailed recommendation on the best strategies to increase uptake.

Short-term

Cultural control - The cultural control techniques proposed are readily available and the efficacy is well understood and integrated on many farms within the UK so this has been grouped as one 'solution.' However, this topic consists of many techniques and studies on the efficacy and cost benefit analysis of integrating techniques such grass/herbal leys into arable systems would be beneficial.

Mechanical weeding - There are a wealth of mechanical weeding options on the market. The use of sophisticated camera guided mechanical weeding is becoming more common in field scale vegetable production, where the higher product value favours the purchase of this equipment. Integration of mechanical weeding into arable systems would require more support and incentivisation for farmers. However, there are now non-organic farmers investing in and using these techniques. A cost-benefit analysis and studies into the combination of mechanical and herbicide-based weed control are required and would be beneficial to improve uptake.

Robotics - Currently the Farm Droid and Robotti are the main, commercially ready, robots available on the UK market. Efficacy and cost-benefit analyses to determine the running costs and the area of land it is possible to cover would clarify if these could be recommended for wider scale adoption in UK arable and horticultural situations. Other technology from Europe should be identified and the potential for UK trials should be explored.

Living mulches – Research into how this could be implemented into UK arable situations is currently ongoing². More work is needed to optimise the practical application and data are required to evaluate the efficacy of weed control compared to other options.

Targeted herbicide application/spot spraying - There are a range of precision application technologies available worldwide to accurately identify and control weeds. John Deere and Agrifac offer real time solutions for arable, Taylor technologies have developed a system for dock control in grassland and VCS (Vegetable Consultancy Service) are currently using a precision sprayer in field vegetables in the UK. There are issues to overcome, such as how to judge chemical requirements, cost of the technology and improving weed identification. It has shown great potential to reduce herbicide use. However, herbicide resistance, particularly to post-emergence herbicides in grass weeds in the UK may reduce its effectiveness and must be considered.

Mulches (non-living/dead) – Plastic and biodegradable mulches can be effective for weed control in high value crops such as vegetables or perennial crop. However, they do have drawbacks, they are expensive, plastics are non-renewable and create high volumes of waste. Biodegradables solve the waste issue, but cost and length of use still need to be considered.

Medium to Long-term

Bioherbicides – Uptake and use of bioherbicides is low in the UK with few commercially available options due to the high costs involved, mainly with product registration. Those that are available are generally non-selective broad-spectrum products such as pelargonic acid and acetic acid. However, these often require multiple applications at high rates therefore restricting interest. Further advances in this field could lead to integration into an IWM system.

Competitive cultivars – The use of competitive cultivars has been shown to decrease black-grass head counts³. More work is required to understand the mechanisms that determine if a variety can suppress weeds or not so that varieties could be rated, similar to the current disease ratings on the UK AHDB recommended list. There is current research into hybrid wheats, that are near to market in the UK, to determine the efficacy of these to suppress weeds.

Flame weeding - Flame weeding is used in organic horticulture systems; however, the cost of fuel is high and driving speed slow, alongside potential environmental concerns will limit wider uptake.

Electrical weeding – this technology is due for commercial release in orchards and vineyards in 2024. ADAS have shown efficacy of previous prototypes but further research is required for the latest technology to inform growers of its efficacy and soil /environmental impact. Machinery for use in row crops is potentially due in 2025.

Laser – Research has shown the potential for using lasers as a non-chemical weed control, however there are no commercially available kits in the UK. EarthRover have been undertaking field trials within the UK for a machine designed for field vegetable production.

3.1.3.2 Policy support for the UK

In addition to the practical / technical solutions outlined in the section above, it is important to consider the barriers highlighted in D2.1. There are a range of considerations to increase the uptake of alternative weed control. Farmers require support to invest in and use new technology that may reduce overall efficacy of weed control and increase labour time when compared to the use of herbicides. For the UK, it is suggested that the following policy implementation would be required to facilitate the increased uptake of alternative weed control methods identified above.

² <https://www.organicresearchcentre.com/our-research/research-project-library/orc-living-mulches/>

³ Lutman PJW, Moss SR, Cook SK, Welham SJ. 2013. A review of the effects of crop agronomy on the management of *Alopecurus myosuroides*. *Weed Research*, 53, 299-313

- **Increase the number of grants for the purchase of equipment.**

Stakeholders considered grants for the purchase of equipment to be useful for the uptake of alternative weed control. Current equipment grants are funded under competitive applications⁴. Widening the scope of uptake would enable more farmers to source grant funding for investment. Currently the Defra Farming Equipment and Technology Fund (FETF 2023) has options for Camera guided inter row sprayers (FETF216P/17P) and for a robotic drill and guided hoe (FETF218P) in arable cropping.

- **Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming (Sustainable Farming Incentives)**

Some alternative approaches have high running costs. The following changes are suggested to help increase uptake; however, stakeholders felt the incentivisation of uptake in the form of grants or taxes would need to be partnered with other factors such as herbicide loss to see widespread adoption of alternative solutions:

- Financial incentives would be the fastest way to increase uptake of alternative weed control methods but source of funding is limited. A small levy on herbicide sales (2%), such as the pesticide tax in Denmark, Sweden, Italy and France⁵, could generate a significant fund for investment in alternatives but this solution is often not seen favourably by UK government.
- Increasing availability of subsidies. Current subsidies are funded under competitive applications and are often catchment specific⁶. The inclusion of 'reduced herbicide usage' payments into future Sustainable Farming Incentive (SFI) schemes, or similar ongoing subsidies, could be used alongside machinery grants to offset higher running costs.

The use of machinery rings/cooperatives was discussed but it was felt incentivisation of these schemes wouldn't increase farmer participation / uptake.

- **Grants for trials of alternative methods**

There is a need for more independent trials to demonstrate the efficacy of solutions before incentivisation begins to determine the most effective solutions. Farmers need confidence in efficacy before investment. However small market opportunities make it difficult to get independent trials producing quality data.

- **Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information**

Farmers need opportunities to see the approach in action before investment. Communication needs to be delivered by organisations and people that farmers trust and be simple, regular and consistent across a wide range of media channels. This requires funding for extension services.

3.1.4 Conclusions for the UK

Each listed solution for the UK NAP will undergo a collaborative assessment through workshops and cost-benefit analysis in WP3. This will provide detailed information on efficacy, the advantages and disadvantages to each solution and the steps needed to implement the solutions in the associated crops. To implement the technical solutions currently available

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/farming-equipment-and-technology-fund-fetf-2023/about-the-farming-equipment-and-technology-fund-fetf-2023>

⁵ <https://www.pan-europe.info/issues/pesticide-taxation>

⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/catchment-sensitive-farming-reduce-agricultural-water-pollution#country-side-stewardship>

it is felt policy recommendations outlined are vital as the current alternative solutions require capital expenditure and higher running / labour costs than the often more favoured herbicide solutions.

3.2 France NAP

3.2.1 Background and Needs

Based on the French survey and focus group results, it appears that farmers are interested in alternative weed control, given herbicide limitations in France. For now, alternative solutions do not satisfy them for many reasons: they are too expensive, time-consuming, and complicated. Moreover, public and customers have a negative opinion on their methods (especially herbicide-based control) and are pushing for a change in their strategies. This makes them look for other solutions. Improvements on current alternative solutions and new innovative ones are required for increasing the overall uptake of non-chemical alternatives. Requirements to support this change towards alternative solutions are listed below:

1. **Farmers need less time-consuming and more effective solutions:** repeated interventions for improved efficiency, and low-working speed, makes labour costs higher in alternative solutions. Alternatives should be as effective as herbicides (in the efficiency-cost-time three-part work).
2. **Farmers need affordable solutions:** alternative solutions are considered more expensive than herbicide use due to tool and machinery purchase costs, requirement for multiple tools, requirement for complementary tactics and associated machines (cover crop management, mechanical weeding...). Moreover, innovative machines like robotics are not yet in a highly competitive market, so these new tools remain expensive for purchase, with high running costs (energy consumption...).
3. **Alternative solutions should be adapted to various farm situations:** small scale farms, sloped fields, climate and soil conditions (competition for water etc.), rocky soil, narrow vineyards.
4. **On-farm testing is necessary for farmers to have confidence before investing.**
5. **Farmers need more information and support to improve the efficiency and uptake of alternative solutions:** fine-tuning, training, reduced crop wound risk, reduced impact on crop, information on available solutions on other advantages or drawbacks, for example the carbon footprint.

3.2.2 Crop selection for France

Viticulture was the main crop for 96% of farmers who completed the survey, whereas cereal/oilseed crops represented only 4%. Most of the non-farmers who responded to the survey and the focus group meeting participants work in the winegrowing sector as advisors, industry representatives or researchers. Given that IFV exclusive sector is vine and wine production, this National Action Plan will include only viticulture.

Among the survey farmers respondents, 61% and 18% follow a conventional and organic management system, respectively. All of them expressed their interest in and need for alternative weed control methods. The survey results showed that there is still a need for raising awareness about the impacts of herbicides, so it is relevant to focus on the alternative solutions, both common and innovative ones, for viticulture, depending on farm sizes, climate and weather conditions.

3.2.3 Solutions for France

Inventoried solutions are mainly technical solutions, matching the needs identified in D2.1. Technical solutions are based on viticulture Oper8 OG solutions listed during the focus group meeting, and solutions available in the D2.2 inventory. In total 22 solutions and barriers have been identified by France (Table 7) and the associated are listed in Table 8.

TABLE 7 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR FRANCE NAP, WITH CURRENT BARRIERS

Technical solutions for France		Barriers					
		Low efficiency	Time	Expensive	No access	Complicated	Impact on crops
1	Mechanical weeding on the row		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Mechanical weeding on the row with complementary hand weeding for perennials		✓	✓		✓	✓
3	Mechanical weeding between the rows						
4	Precision weeding through row identification by camera or GPS use		✓	✓			
5	Robotics (currently only for the row)		✓	✓			
6	Thermal weeding		✓	✓			
7	Electrical weeding		✓	✓		✓	
8	Pelargonic acid	✓	✓	✓		✓	
9	Targeted herbicides by hand (complementary to other solutions)		✓				
10	Cover crop sowed on the row (hydro-mulching...)		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
11	Green manure between the rows (mechanically destroyed in spring)						
12	Green manure between the rows for mulch between the rows						✓
13	Green manure mulch on the row (displaced from inter-row cover crop)				✓		✓
14	Mowing on the row		✓		✓	✓	✓
15	Mowing between the rows of permanent grasses		✓				
16	Natural fibres mulches (fetch, wool, starch)	✓	✓	✓		✓	
17	Straw mulches	✓	✓	✓		✓	
18	Wood chips mulches		✓	✓		✓	
19	Vegetal waste mulch (slightly composted)	✓	✓			✓	
20	Plastic mulches					✓	
21	Mixed solutions herbicide / mechanical weeding						

22	Winter grazing						✓	
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TABLE 8: THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR FRANCE NAP MATCHING THE RELATED NEEDS.

Technical solutions for France	Associated needs
Mechanical weeding solutions	>Training of engine users and fine-tuning of machines >Peer-to-peer learning >Subsidies to enhance engine sharing and support service providers >Grants for purchase of equipment and covering the running costs >R&D on tools to prevent wounds and improve efficacy around the trunks
Precision weeding through row identification by camera or GPS use	>Subsidies for access to innovative tools >R&D on innovative tools >Trials and grants for trials for developing and adapting these tools
Robotics (currently only for the row)	>Changes in regulations to allow robots to run autonomously alone in the field >Grants for purchase of equipment
Thermal and electrical weeding	>Trials and grants for trials: good efficiency is not shown yet >R&D to lower energy-consumption and improve efficiency >Demo-events
Pelargonic acid	>Trials on local scales >Trials on perennial weeds
Cover crops (green manure, permanent grass)	>R&D on cover crop species adapted for vine >R&D on cover crop management tools >Increase of facilities and seeds providers >Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming practices >Trials for local contexts
Mowing on the row	>R&D on tools for row mowing, training of users
Dead mulches (plastic mulch not included)	>Subsidies for environmentally farming practices >Trials and R&D for mulch types
Mixed solutions herbicide / mechanical weeding	>Changes in regulations to allow an appropriate use of herbicides (preventing herbicide resistance...) for combined solutions
Winter grazing	>Facilities and service providers (shepherd, fences...) are required to make this technique easy-of-access

3.2.3.1 Technical 'on-farm' solutions

- **Mechanical weeding solutions**

Both inter and intra row weeders are commonly available alternative solutions. Nevertheless, mechanical weeding solutions have multiple options (hydraulic tools, passive tools), and are still considered complicated and possibly harmful for the crop. Moreover, other considerations about carbon footprint and impact on soil are keeping some farmers from using them. Therefore, mechanical weeding solutions need further assessment, to evaluate which conditions and contexts they are suited to and where improvements can be made.

- **Mulches**

Trials are currently running on mulches, but costs related to purchase, implementation, and limited long-lasting effects, are still preventing farmers from considering it as a solution.

- **Cover crops and mowing**

The uptake of cover crops solutions varies between region, climate and weather conditions. It appears to be an efficient solution to limit the use of herbicide and mechanical weeding between the rows, but it is not yet common to use it on the rows. Several solutions have been tested through different cover crop species.

- **Targeted herbicides**

For viticulture, targeted herbicides are complementary localised treatments on perennial weeds made by hand that can be used as part of a IWM strategy.

- **Robotics**

Robots are a new innovation, and the uptake is currently limited.

- **Bio-herbicides**

Pelargonic acid solutions are in development, and current trials aim at defining the best application conditions to increase their efficacy.

- **Grazing**

This solution is for situations where shepherds are available. It is currently possible only before budburst.

3.2.3.2 Policy support

The needs associated to the solutions request policy support to go with them. Subsidies for alternative practices currently exist and should continue to support the purchase of equipment and covering the additional running costs. Grants and incentives for environmentally friendly farming is also a solution to support the general additional costs of alternative farming strategies. Grants for trials and R&D projects for improving efficiency remains necessary. Trials would demonstrate which techniques produce consistent results and demo-events provide cross-fertilization between peers, advisors, farmers, and researchers.

3.2.4 Conclusions for France

Each listed solution will undergo a collaborative assessment through workshops and cost-benefit analysis in WP3. This will provide relevant information on different advantages, efficiency, environmental impact, among others, and help to compare the solutions for developing strategies adapted to different local contexts.

3.3 Italy NAP

3.3.1 Background and Needs

In Italy farmers showed an interest in testing alternative weed control solutions, but their adoption was considered constrained by economic, operational and knowledge limitations.

The major needs identified in the stakeholders' survey and in the focus group meetings were:

- Selecting quick operations to tackle weeds at the right moment with the degree of success being not significantly hampered by weather conditions ("Methods are time consuming").
- Making alternative solutions cheaper ("Solutions are too expensive").
- Getting familiar with solutions before adoption/purchase ("No opportunity to test innovative solutions before investing in them").

- Enhancing the offer of advanced solutions on the market or favoring cooperation among farmers (“No access to required equipment”).
- Being guided in application of alternative methods (“No skilled advisors available”).
- Getting in touch with alternative solutions (“Lack of information”).

3.3.2 Crop selection for Italy

In Italy vineyards were selected as the main crop because it is the focus of our OG. However, we will include arable crops and field vegetables in the NAP, thanks to available expertise in the local research team and good representation of specialised farmers and other stakeholders for these crop typologies in the NN and in the focus group. Moreover, as reported in D2.2, in Italy there is great interest in all the crops selected for the NAP.

3.3.3 Solutions for Italy

A comprehensive list of technical (21) and political (7) solutions are provided in Table 9.

TABLE 9 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR THE ITALY NAP

<i>Solutions for Italy</i>		<i>Cropping system</i>		
	<i>Technical solutions</i>	<i>Vineyards</i>	<i>Field vegetables</i>	<i>Arable</i>
1	Inter row mechanical weeding based on precision farming (e.g., inter-row cultivation coupled with camera guided)		✓	✓
2	Intra-row mechanical weeding for high density vineyards	✓		
3	Intra-row mechanical weeding for row crops		✓	✓
4	Intra-row flaming	✓	✓	
5	Hot foam/ Electrocutation/Laser weeding/Steaming	✓	✓	
6	Tillage systems	✓	✓	✓
7	Robotics	✓	✓	✓
8	Crop Rotations (including perennial legumes)		✓	✓
9	Bioherbicides (pelargonic acid) and allelopathic compounds	✓	✓	✓
10	Under-row self-reseeding cover crops	✓		
11	Living mulch (whole surface)		✓	✓
12	Living mulch (under-row)	✓		
13	Cover crop-derived dead mulch (whole surface)	✓	✓	✓

14	Cover crop-derived dead mulch (inter-row)	✓		
15	Cover crop-derived dead mulch (under-row)	✓		
16	Mulch material (no cover crop-derived: e.g. plastic or bioplastic film, straw, etc.)		✓	
17	Green manures	✓	✓	✓
18	False seedbed		✓	✓
19	Variety selection		✓	✓
20	Seed selection (e.g., purity of seeds, cured seeds)	✓	✓	✓
21	Solarization (including bio-solarization)		✓	
Political Solutions				
1	Increase the number of grants to implement the farmer's equipment	✓	✓	✓
2	Subsidies for training and technical consultancy	✓	✓	✓
3	Create added value for products cultivated through alternative control methods (public or private product labels)	✓	✓	✓
4	Boost demonstrative events (through universities and research institutes)	✓	✓	✓
5	Incentives for machinery companies to develop more efficient equipment (also in terms of higher timeliness)	✓	✓	✓
6	Favour the creation of value chains with diversified crop production so that to enable crop rotation (i.e., creating real market opportunities for more crops)		✓	✓
7	Allowing organic farmers to buy also non-organic cover crops seeds	✓	✓	✓

3.3.3.1 Technical 'on-farm' Solutions

The participants of the Italian survey and the focus group members selected mostly direct physical (mechanical + thermal) and cultural weed control methods. Advanced technology was also mentioned in combination with machinery for precision hoeing/cultivation. UAV- or sensors-based technologies for weed monitoring/detection were never mentioned, possibly due to the mean low acreage of Italian farms. This is considered as a constraint for the technical efficacy and economic efficiency of precision farming technologies (i.e., low return of investments).

The main technical solutions can be summarized as follow:

- *New technologies* like flaming, precision hoeing, electrical weeding, bioherbicides, solarization, laser, hot foam, allelopathy
- *Mechanical means* like ploughing, chiseling, hoeing, shredding, mowing, harrowing

- *Cultural means* like crop rotations, cover crops, false seedbed, rotation, intercropping, delayed sowing, mulch material, dead mulch, living mulch, green manure, sowing density
- *Genetic selection of crops (cover crop included)*

In many cases, the identified solutions were applicable to different crop types (vines and herbaceous crops). In the case of time-consuming and expensive methods (e.g., laser weeding, hot foam, flaming, electrical weeding), the solutions were applicable only to vineyards and field vegetables, because they are considered as high value crops, with sufficient levels of farmer return in face of huge monetary investments necessary to implement the solutions.

In vineyards, mechanical weeding and cover crops were split according to the treated area (i.e., under-row or inter-row) as this makes a huge difference in the design and implementation of the technique. One of the solutions tested in the Italian OG fell into the category of under-row self-reseeding cover crops in vineyards.

Cultural methods implying diversification of cropping systems (e.g., crop rotation, intercropping, cover crops and green manures), field and soil management (e.g., tillage), cultivar choice and crop establishment technique (e.g., delayed sowing) were mentioned many times by stakeholders. However, these methods were often described as “complex”, “difficult to set” or with low economic return. This latter comment applied to crop rotation, that was considered worthy to be implemented only in the presence of market value for additional crops besides the main grown crop.

Interestingly, variety choice and seed selection were mentioned as key methods also linked to cover crops. This reveals the big interest in these agronomic tools across all the crop types, but also unravels a risk perceived by farmers that low quality cover crop seeds can increase the weed seedbank, instead of helping in its reduction.

3.3.3.2 Policy support

Possible levers identified include the production of new knowledge for those solutions for which poor information is currently available. One way could be to boost the case-sensitive, and locally fine-tuned research and demonstration trials. From the survey conducted on stakeholders’ perception, unlocking the access to subsidies for facilitating availability of new technologies came out as one of the key levers. The most important stakeholders’ needs identified within the survey and the focus group discussion follows below:

- Grants for the purchase of equipment: selected by more than 80% of the farmers, linked to the high cost barrier both for current and alternative methods.
- Consultations with a specialist or experienced user: more than 70% of the farmers expressed this preference, as they need support for adopting novel strategies, especially in the transition phase or more regularly for long-term perspective methods, such as cultural control.
- Trials of alternative weed control methods: linked to lack of information and proof of efficacy, possibly connected to the idea of on-farm trials and learning by doing approach (‘on the job’ learning).
- Demonstration events of the methods of interest: related to the need of peer-to-peer knowledge transfer and of showcasing.
- Grants to establish trials to evaluate the effectiveness of the solutions: related to the need of local fine-tuning of alternative method in the specific farmers’ conditions.
- Less strict rules on organic origin of cover crop seeds to reduce their purchase costs and to increase their purity.

3.3.4 Conclusions for Italy

The listed technical solutions will be participatorily assessed in national workshops in WP3. Special emphasis will be given to adaptability to the variety of pedoclimatic and socio-economic contexts that characterise the country and its traditional crops. Political solutions will be considered also with respect to the existing policy measures which are in place at national/regional level as part of agro-climatic measures framed by Rural Development Programs (RDPs).

3.4 Greece NAP

3.4.1 Background and Needs

Chemical herbicides play an important role in weed control in Greece. Despite their advantages, their extended use and overreliance on chemical control without the integration with agronomic practices resulted in the development of herbicide resistant weeds and some phytotoxicity issues. Furthermore, the ban of several active ingredients and the loss of the registration along with the increasing cost and the health concerns highlight the importance of potential weed management alternatives. Greek farmers were interested in alternative weed control methods, but several specific needs and issues were identified from the surveys:

1. Access to information and concerns about effectiveness.
2. Skilled advisors are required.
3. Demonstration and trials are necessary.
4. Financial support is crucial for the adoption of non-chemical alternatives.
5. Public perception should be considered.
6. Peer influence is always important.

3.4.2 Crop selection for Greece

In Greece the original OGs research was in field vegetables in which non-chemical alternatives are important due to the few chemical options. Weed control is far more intensive in arable cropping and vineyards/orchards. Of the 64 farmers that completed the survey (D2.1), 35% indicated that cereals were their main crop, with vineyards (18%) and orchards (17%) being very important for the Greek and wider Mediterranean agriculture. To maximise the benefit of this NAP we have therefore chosen to concentrate on field vegetables, vineyards and orchards, with cereals as a 3rd crop choice.

3.4.3 Solutions for Greece

There are 13 solutions selected for Greece shown in Table 10, including technical and political solutions.

TABLE 10 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR THE GREECE NAP

	<i>Solutions for Greece</i>	<i>Cropping system</i>		
		<i>Field vegetables</i>	<i>Vineyards/ orchards</i>	<i>Cereals</i>
	<i>Technical solutions</i>			
1	Mechanical weeding	✓		
2	Cover crops	✓	✓	
3	Variety selection (competitive cultivars)	✓		✓
4	Pelargonic Acid	✓	✓	
5	Hot Foam	✓	✓	
6	Crop rotation	✓		✓
7	False seedbed	✓		✓

8	Precision spraying			
9	Mixed systems (minimum use of herbicides combined with mechanical weeding or cover crops)			
<i>Political Solutions</i>				
1	Increase the number of grants to implement the farmer's equipment	✓	✓	✓
2	Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information	✓	✓	✓
3	Improving Access to information	✓	✓	✓
4	Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	✓	✓	✓

3.4.3.1 Technical 'on-farm' Solutions

- **Mechanical weeding solutions**

This technique is mainly used between the rows, and it is already a well-used alternative solution. However, there are few options or tools within the row. Nevertheless, mechanical weeding solutions have multiple options (hydraulic tools, passive tools), and are still considered complicated and possibly harmful for the crop. Moreover, other considerations about carbon footprint and impact on soil erosion (due to high slopes) seem to make this choice declining in popularity.

- **Cover crops**

The uptake of cover crops solutions varies between region and climate and weather conditions. In general, mostly winter cover crops can be used in order to avoid moisture loss and ensure successful establishment and growth. It appears to be an efficient solution to limit the use of herbicide and mechanical weeding between the rows, but it is not yet widely used. Several solutions have been tested using different cover crop species and mixtures.

- **Variety selection**

Competitive cultivars of cereals and field vegetables do play an important role in weed suppression. Furthermore, allelopathic cultivars need to be evaluated and used, with a special focus on crop rotation systems.

- **Pelargonic acid**

Pelargonic acid solutions are in development, and current trials aim at defining the best application conditions to increase their efficacy. For the farmers it is very important to reduce the cost and avoid the repeated applications required.

- **Hot foam**

This solution is up to now only experimental. There is a huge interest, especially for viticulture, however the cost for the equipment is not yet affordable for individual farmers. It also requires a large quantity of water to be transported.

- **Crop rotation**

Crop rotation has been underestimated for many decades due to the dominance of chemical control and the subsidies of specific crops. Lately, farmers are interested in smart rotation schemes in order to control noxious weeds and ensure high crop yields.

- **False seedbed**

Almost unknown cultural practice but of high interest for crops like rice and winter cereals. The further improvement of the practice in order to avoid tillage and manage to control a wide range of weeds is required.

- **Precision spraying**

There are available technologies on market today in EU and globally. However, they are still not widely known and demonstrated in Greece. Efficacy and cost-benefit analyses to determine the running costs would clarify if this could be recommended for wider scale adoption in Greece.

- **Mixed systems**

Mixed systems are usually characterized those in which the use of herbicides (preferably minimum) is combined with mechanical weeding or cover crops. It is a very popular approach for Greek farmers due to the importance of the perennial-permanent crops. However, the method should be further optimised, evaluated and demonstrated in a range of pedoclimatic conditions.

3.4.3.2 Policy support

Enhancing Equipment Implementation Grants: We should consider augmenting the funding available for grants aimed at facilitating the adoption of modern farming equipment by farmers. These grants could encompass a range of agricultural machinery and technologies, including but not limited to advanced tractors, precision planting tools, and automated irrigation systems. This financial support will help farmers access and integrate state-of-the-art equipment into their farming practices, ultimately boosting efficiency and productivity.

Supporting Farmer Demonstration Events: Farmer-led demonstration events are a crucial aspect of disseminating knowledge about innovative and sustainable farming techniques. By increasing the number of grants allocated for organizing these events, we can encourage farmers to share their experiences and showcase alternative agricultural methods. This knowledge-sharing can significantly benefit the wider farming community by promoting best practices and fostering collaboration among farmers.

Improving Access to Information: Access to accurate and up-to-date information is essential for farmers to make informed decisions about their farming practices. Therefore, part of the grant allocation should focus on developing accessible information dissemination channels. This may include online resources, workshops, training programs, and the establishment of local information centres. These initiatives will empower farmers with the knowledge they need to adopt more efficient and sustainable farming methods.

Subsidizing Environmentally Friendly Farming: To incentivize environmentally friendly practices, subsidies can be provided to farmers who adopt sustainable farming techniques for alternative weed control. These subsidies could cover a range of eco-friendly practices such as organic farming, reduced pesticide and chemical fertilizer usage, and conservation tillage methods. Encouraging such practices not only benefits the environment but also aligns with consumer preferences for more sustainable and healthy food production.

3.4.4 Conclusions for Greece

In Greece, the realm of agricultural research initially focused on field vegetables, where non-chemical alternatives held particular importance due to limited options. However, it is essential to recognize that weed control becomes even more intensive in arable cropping, vineyards, and orchards, which play a vital role in both Greek and broader Mediterranean agriculture. A strategic decision was made to concentrate our efforts on field vegetables, vineyards (and orchards), with cereals as a valuable third crop choice. The investigation of alternative weed control methods has revealed a diverse array of approaches with varying degrees of adoption and effectiveness. Mechanical weeding solutions have found their niche, particularly between rows, yet challenges remain regarding their complexity and potential crop impact. The environmental concerns surrounding carbon footprint and soil erosion have also sparked debates around their popularity. Cover crops offer

promise, especially in regions with specific climate and weather conditions, as they can help reduce the need for herbicides and mechanical weeding, though their adoption remains somewhat limited.

Variety selection has emerged as an important aspect, with competitive cultivars demonstrating potential in weed suppression. The introduction of allelopathic cultivars and a focus on crop rotation schemes can further enhance weed control strategies. The development of pelargonic acid solutions is ongoing, with trials aimed at optimizing their application conditions to reduce costs and minimize the need for repeated treatments.

Intriguingly, hot foam solutions show promise, particularly in viticulture, although their adoption is currently limited due to equipment costs. Crop rotation, a practice previously underestimated in favour of chemical control, is experiencing renewed interest, as farmers explore intelligent rotation schemes for effective weed management. Additionally, the lesser-known practice of false seedbed preparation holds potential, especially for crops like rice and winter cereals, with room for improvement to reduce tillage and expand its applicability. Precision spraying and mixed systems have also a potential with their adoption depending on the cost, technical optimization and demonstration activities.

As we move forward, policy support becomes instrumental in facilitating the adoption of these alternative weed control methods. Enhancing grants for equipment implementation, supporting farmer-led demonstration events, improving access to information, and providing subsidies for environmentally friendly farming practices can collectively empower Greek farmers to embrace sustainable and effective weed management strategies. Multiple solution choices are available, having various barriers to overcome. Farmers and stakeholders ask for economical support and demo trials-training to get knowledge on the several alternatives. By combining research insights with robust policy measures, we can pave the way for a more resilient and environmentally conscious agricultural sector in Greece.

3.5 Latvia NAP

3.5.1 Background and Needs

The following needs and gaps were identified from the survey results (D2.1) for Latvia.

1. Farmers need greater confidence in the efficacy of alternative weed control methods.
2. Farmers need access to alternative weed control equipment.
3. Farmers need affordable alternative solutions for weed control.
4. Farmers need alternative solutions that have at least equal effectiveness and time consumption as herbicides to implement.
5. Farmers need more information on alternative weed control solutions. They need to see these solutions on their farms in cooperation with scientifically based methodology and rating of its efficiency on different soils, in different fields/crops/weeds.

3.5.2 Crop selection for Latvia

As specified in Part 2 of this report, Latvia has chosen to focus on field vegetables and arable crops (Table 5). There have been 20 solutions selected for Latvia (Table 11) and we have chosen to break these down into both technical and political solutions based on the feedback from our survey and focus group results (D2.1). These consider the five needs highlighted for Latvia with an aim to address those needs.

3.5.3 Solutions for Latvia

The selected solutions for Latvia are shown below in Table 11.

TABLE 11 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR LATVIA NAP

<i>Solutions for Latvia</i>		<i>Cropping system</i>	
<i>Technical solutions</i>		<i>Field vegetables</i>	<i>Arable</i>
1	Precision spraying: available equipment, demonstrations, subsidies	✓	✓
2	Bioherbicides: efficacy demonstrations on field. Environmental impact analysis and cost benefit analysis required.	✓	✓
3	Inter row mechanical weeding based on precision farming (e.g., inter-row cultivation coupled with camera guided) wider dissemination of information on efficacy, carbon footprint, efficiency, time to manage (period of use)		✓
4	Intra-row mechanical weeding for row crops		✓
5	Mixed solutions herbicide / mechanical weeding	✓	✓
6	Robotics: Demonstration and promotion of available kit and of new emerging technologies from other countries for different crops.	✓	✓
7	Cover crops: efficacy demonstrations on field, wider dissemination of information on efficacy, demonstration on farms	✓	✓
8	Intercropping: efficacy demonstrations on field, dissemination of information on efficacy, demonstration on farms, information about available equipment	✓	✓
9	Competitive cultivars/enhanced plant breeding- development of new plant breeding, demonstration of the results	✓	✓
10	Laser weeder for carrots, beetroots, spinach	✓	
11	Cultural control (delay drilling in cereals)- efficacy trials	✓	✓
12	Seed rate and interrow distance efficacy trials	✓	✓
13	Electrical weeding	✓	✓
14	Intra-row flaming	✓	✓
15	Crop Rotations (including perennial legumes)		✓
<i>Political Solutions</i>			
1	Increase the number of grants for the purchase of equipment	✓	✓
2	Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	✓	✓
3	Robust independent trial (scientifically justified) data to quantify the efficacy of alternative methods	✓	✓
4	Grants for trials of alternative methods for demonstrations and scientifically approved data	✓	✓

5	Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information	✓	✓
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3.5.3.1 Technical ‘on-farm’ Solutions

In Latvia the original OGs research was in carrots (laser weeding). However, weed control in small grain cereals is more crucial to Latvia as these are the most dominant crops. From answers of 91 farmers that completed the survey (D2.1), 85% indicated that cereals and oilseeds were the main crop and 65% of the scientific papers in D2.2 referred to arable crops. To maximise the benefit of this NAP we have therefore chosen to concentrate on arable and horticultural crops in Latvia.

The solutions identified have been grouped into short and medium-long term. For the short-term solutions, we recommend carrying out cost/benefit analysis to determine the efficacy, costs, environmental impacts and best practises of the technologies, alongside the data gathered from T2.2 and T2.3. This would refine the information to give a more detailed recommendation on the best strategies to promote to increase uptake.

Short-term

- **Precision spraying/targeted application (patch spraying/spot spraying)**

There are available technologies on market today in EU and other countries. Using the resources developed in WP 2.2 and 2.3 techniques should be analysed to determine the best practise solutions. Currently Weed-IT, John Deere, BASF, Greeneye Technology is available on the EU market. All the equipment can be ordered to Latvia, but they are not spread out and demonstrated in Latvia very much. Efficacy and cost-benefit analyses to determine the running costs would clarify if this could be recommended for wider scale adoption in Latvian arable situations. There is a need of demonstrations and popularization of such technologies.

- **Mechanical weeding** (with and without camera guided).

There is an abundance of mechanical weeding options. These could be grouped into spring/comb harrows, inter row hoes and camera guided hoes. Using the resources developed in WP 2.2 and 2.3 techniques should be analysed to determine the best practise solutions. Risks about greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and soil health should be considered.

- **Robotics**

Currently the FarmDroid, Carbon Robotics and Naio Technologies are the main, commercially ready robots available on the EU market. All the equipment can be ordered to Latvia, but they are not spread out and demonstrated in Latvia. Efficacy and cost-benefit analyses to determine the running costs and the area of land it is possible to cover would clarify if this could be recommended for wider scale adoption in Latvian arable situations. Other technology from Europe should be identified and the potential for Latvian trials should be explored.

- **Laser weeders**

Carbon Robotics ‘WeedBot’ is available on market for use on vegetables. This equipment should be tested in Latvian conditions. There is a need of demonstrations and popularization of such technologies.

- **Bioherbicides**

There is a need to make demonstrations of pelargonic acid to prove its efficiency in Latvian climatic conditions.

Medium to Long-term

- Bioherbicides – new biopesticides should be developed with lower impact on the environment and human health, procedure of the registration should be improved.
- Competitive cultivars – National crop breeding programs should include the development of crops (mostly cereals, vegetables, and potatoes) with increased weed tolerance or the increasing of allelopathic features in crop rotation systems.

3.5.3.2 Policy support for Latvia

In addition to the practical / technical solutions outlined in the section above, it is important to consider the barriers highlighted in D2.1. There are a range of considerations to increase the uptake of alternative weed control. Farmers require support to invest in and use new technology that may reduce overall efficacy of weed control and increase labour time when compared to the use of herbicides. For Latvia it is suggested that the following policy implementation would be required to facilitate the increased uptake of alternative weed control methods identified above.

- **Increase the number of grants for the purchase of equipment**

Stakeholders believed equipment grants to be helpful for spreading alternative weed control methods. Grants for modern equipment are supported by competitive applications. A wider range of adoption would make it easier for more farmers to get grant money for investment. Currently under the governmental subsidies mostly it is possible to buy harrowing (EINBOECK, METAI-TECHNIK, QUIVOGNE, JAR-MET, DUVELSDORF, EXPOM, AGRISEM, WEAVING MACHINERY, HATZENBICHLER, etc.) and inter row camera guided or other system guided harrower. No precise sprayers are available. 'Farm Droid' - a solar-driven field robot that seeds and weeds is available also under subsidies.

- **Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming**

Some alternative methods have considerable operating expenses. The following adjustments are suggested to encourage uptake; nevertheless, stakeholders noted that in order to see broad adoption of alternative solutions, other considerations, such as herbicide loss, would need to be linked with grants or levies that encourage uptake:

- Financial incentives would be the fastest way to increase uptake of alternative weed control methods, but source of funding is limited.
- Increasing availability of subsidies. Current subsidies are funded under competitive applications and are often catchment specific⁷. The inclusion of 'reduced herbicide usage' payments into future ECO schemes, or similar ongoing subsidies, could be used alongside machinery grants to offset higher running costs.
- **Grants for trials of alternative methods**

There is a need for more independent trials (scientifically proven) to demonstrate the efficacy of solutions. Farmers need confidence in efficacy before investment. However small market opportunities make it difficult to get independent trials producing quality data.

- **Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information**

Farmers need opportunities to see the approach in action before investment. Communication needs to be delivered by organisations and people that farmers trust and be simple, regular and consistent across a wide range of media channels. This requires funding for extension services.

⁷ <https://www.lad.gov.lv/lv/katalogs/41-atbalsts-ieguldijumiem-lauku-saimniecibas>

3.5.3.3 Policy support

Policy support is needed for the new equipment introduction into the farming systems for different kinds of farmers with different farm sizes. There should be Eco schemes to support farmers willing to reduce the pesticide usage. More demonstrations with ready solutions should be available at country level to persuade farmers to introduce new efficient techniques. There should be not only the economically driven factors, but also farmers will and understanding of the need to reduce the pesticide load on human health and environment. Therefore, a life cycle assessment (LCA) and cost benefit analysis of the alternative methods, showing the undoubted positive impact of reduction of pesticide usage should be made.

3.5.4 Conclusions for Latvia

There is a big potential for mechanical weed control, because of the availability of the equipment. There is still a doubt of the efficacy of perennial weed control (for example, *Elytrigia repens*) without herbicides. Therefore, there is a potential for integrated weed control using herbicides and mechanical weed control. Bioherbicides must be more widely available. Laser weeding robots for field vegetables (carrots, beetroots, spinach) have great potential and can be potentially used on big farms, where investments are economically viable. Robot usage for weed control in vegetables also has a need in Latvia due to labour shortage. Farmers have a great interest in spot spraying, as this can lead to high reduction of pesticide use, without the need to change a lot the previous experience and knowledge.

3.6 Sweden NAP

3.6.1 Background and Needs

The needs and gaps for alternative weed control in Sweden were highlighted in D2.1 and are listed below:

1. Cropping systems in Sweden need to be more diverse to be able to reduce the use of herbicides and to think about acceptable weed thresholds in crops.
2. Technology such as row hoes are not used practical to a large extent.
3. Focus on the herbicides that are dominant and that cause most of the problems. In Sweden seven substances constitute 60% of the herbicide use.
4. The less sophisticated solutions (adjustment of sprayers, choice of nozzles etc.) could lead to substantial reduction of herbicide use. It also essential to get different components to work together in a more efficient manner. When it comes to spraying technology, we have seen much less progress in terms of precision agriculture compared with fertilizing. It is essential to not only emphasize on new technology, since technology is only replaced very slowly. For instance, in Sweden, 150 new sprayers are sold each year, whereas about 6000 sprayers are in use regularly.
5. Uptake of new technology such as drones to establish weed management zones or robots. One aspect that is important is that in many crops there is a lack of staff, so that the manual work actually needs to be replaced.
6. From a resistance point of view, it is better to avoid one spraying occasion instead of lowering the dose. In horticultural crops and sugar beets in Sweden, there is a high demand on keeping the crops free from weeds, and the use of herbicides are often combined with mechanical solutions.

3.6.2 Crop selection for Sweden

The original OGs research was in cereals and cereals and oilseeds were also the most common crop among the farmers completing the survey (D2.1). However, sugar beets and potatoes are also important crops and in sugar beet in particular there are many initiatives on how to reduce the use of herbicides. The third crop category that we would like to focus on are the field grown vegetables. Although they are not that economically very important for Sweden as a whole, the alternative weed control methods are very much in focus here since the herbicide usage is considerable and the use of manual weeding techniques are difficult to continue because of labour scarcity.

3.6.3 Solutions for Sweden

Technical solutions are summarized from the survey, while the political solutions are items gathered primarily from the Focus Group discussion (Table 12). The solutions are arranged in decreasing order of importance. The list is also somewhat influenced by similar surveys performed in Sweden.

TABLE 12 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR SWEDEN NAP

<i>Solutions for Sweden</i>		<i>Cropping system</i>		
	<i>Technical solutions</i>	<i>Arable</i>	<i>Potatoes/sugar beet</i>	<i>Field vegetables</i>
1	Mechanical weeding (including camera guided systems)	✓	✓	✓
2	Targeted herbicide applications/Spot-spraying (using either maps to produce application files or spray on the go using	✓		
3	Robots		✓	✓
4	Cultural control (crop rotations, delayed seeding, perennial crops, sub-crops)	✓	✓	✓
5	Bioherbicides	✓		✓
6	Mulches			✓
7	Laser weeder			✓
8	Hot water/foam			✓
<i>Political Solutions</i>				
1	Enhance the focus on proper handling of spraying equipment to lower the doses and to encourage the use of nozzles with	✓	✓	✓
2	Subsidies for environmental farming. It is claimed to be an efficient way to increase the uptake of this technology.	✓	✓	✓
3	Demos incl. farm visits “best practice”	✓	✓	✓
4	Grants for technical support to take up alternative solutions	✓	✓	✓
5	Control of the IPM-implementations. It is compulsory to use IPM, not always fulfilled. Stricter control required.	✓	✓	✓

3.6.3.1 Technical 'on-farm' solutions

In Sweden there is both a focus and an interest in the techniques that are not that advanced and that can reach some distance without huge investments. What belongs to this category is the use of adjustable nozzles. They encourage the use of less herbicides during courses in spraying technology and also courses in proper handling of application files for site-specific spraying. It is well known that there is a lack of technical skills among farmers that may be the most important obstacle for taking up the technique to lower the use of herbicides.

There are several solutions that today makes it possible to spray site-specifically, using drones or four-wheeled motorbikes to collect data and to produce application files afterwards (Cultivise (DK), Oper-8 OG and Datalogisk (DK)). These techniques could reach more customers provided it can be proven that it is not too complicated, costly and that the risk for losing yield or money is minimal. To reach this, independent demos are needed.

There are also solutions with cameras attached to spraying boom like DAT Ecopatch for row-specific application of herbicides. These techniques are mostly developed for cereals and there are also possibilities to use camera or GNSS assisted hoes such as System Cameleon.

Robots, primarily for field grown vegetables, are also emerging on the Swedish market, most common are Farm Droid and Ekobot. Another alternative is Robotti from Agrobot.

3.6.3.2 Policy support

It is considered very important to support the transition to a lesser use of herbicides by policies, such as subsidies for purchase of equipment and technical support. A system that has been proposed in the Swedish Focus Group is the IP-suisse, (<https://www.ipsuisse.ch/>). Demonstrations for getting to know the different techniques is also considered important. Long-term trials to prove how cost-efficient the different methods are would also be helpful when deciding on the choice of technology.

One thing that was also mentioned in the Swedish Focus Group is that it is wise to concentrate on the most problematic herbicide compounds first. For instance, the reduction of the use of glyphosate is high up on the agenda and in Sweden this compound constitutes a large percentage of the total use of herbicides.

3.6.4 Conclusions for Sweden

In the short term, it is thought that the camera-assisted or GNSS-assisted hoes will become more common, along with the use of robots primarily for field grown vegetables. Patch-spraying, using cameras for distributing glyphosate after harvest is also quite straight forward and could be taken up rather easily. Cameras on the spray-boom seems also manageable in relatively short term.

Regarding the techniques using maps for site-specific spraying, the future is more uncertain and it will probably take longer before they are used to a large extent. The use of drones for direct spraying is also likely to take longer before it can be used in practice, as it requires regulatory approval.

In all cases it is important both with subsidies of different kinds to encourage the uptake of the technology and also to encourage the technical support both in short-term to use the currently available technique the most efficiently.

3.7 Spain NAP

3.7.1 Background and Needs

The Spanish agricultural sector has traditionally relied upon chemical herbicides as a primary means of weed management. However, recent years have witnessed a growing awareness of the associated health and environmental

risks. This increased awareness has underscored the need to explore alternative weed control methods that are not only more environmentally friendly but also cost-effective for farmers.

Consequently, Spanish farmers are acutely conscious of the potential hazards associated with herbicide usage, with only a minimal 5% expressing disagreement with this sentiment (T2.1), and an equal percentage indicating strong disagreement. Nevertheless, despite concerns regarding the cumulative impact of herbicides, they remain the most widely employed method among Spanish respondents, with 38% citing their convenience and effectiveness in weed population management, thereby saving valuable time and labour resources.

However, it is essential to note that Spanish farmers have voiced concerns over the drawbacks of herbicides, including their high cost, detrimental environmental effects, and lack of societal acceptance. These concerns have prompted a heightened interest among Spanish farmers in exploring alternative weed control methods, leading to the identification of specific needs based on survey data.

1. Alternative weed control methods need to be more cost effective.
2. Alternative weed control methods are too time consuming, so demonstration of long-term efficacy compared to herbicides is required.
3. Farmers require incentives to sow more perennial crops.
4. There is a lack of confidence in alternative weed control methods as farmers would prefer to learn from other farmers that are using methods successfully.
5. More training/guidance and sharing of practical experience and expertise required on alternative methods.

3.7.2 Crop selection for Spain

In the context of Spain, the CONTECAD OG research initially focused on weed control methods in horticultural crops, specifically employing essential oils. However, it was recognized that weed control held significant importance in vineyards and arable farming as well. Among the 31 surveyed farmers (D2.1), 29% identified vineyards as their primary crop, while 22% were primarily engaged in cereals and oilseeds production. Furthermore, scientific literature in D2.2 demonstrated that arable crops featured prominently, accounting for 65% of the represented research papers.

In order to maximize the efficacy of the Spanish National Action Plan (NAP), our strategic decision has been to emphasize research and development efforts in vineyards and horticultural crops as the primary focus areas, with arable crops considered as a viable third option. This approach ensures that we align our resources with the sectors where weed control solutions are most urgently needed and have the greatest potential for impact.

3.7.3 Solutions for Spain

There are 13 selected solutions for Spain shown below in Table 13.

TABLE 13 THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS FOR SPAIN NAP

		<i>Solutions for Spain</i>			<i>Cropping system</i>		
		<i>Technical solutions</i>	<i>Horticultural crops</i>	<i>Vineyards</i>	<i>Arable</i>		
1	Mechanical weeding. Including Inter row mechanical weeding based on precision farming (e.g., inter-row cultivation coupled with camera guided tools)		✓			✓	
2	Targeted herbicides		✓	✓		✓	
3	Cultural control		✓	✓		✓	

4	Mulching with wood chips and herbs	✓	✓	
5	Silvopastoral methods (involving livestock/poultry)	✓	✓	
6	Variety selection	✓		✓
7	Robotics	✓	✓	✓
8	Bioherbicides (essential oils)	✓	✓	
Political Solutions				
1	Subsidies for environmentally friendly farming	✓	✓	✓
2	Increase the number of grants to implement the farmer's equipment	✓	✓	✓
3	Improving the advisory services on IWM practices	✓	✓	✓
4	Grants for trials of alternative methods	✓	✓	✓
5	Demonstration events of alternative methods and access to information	✓	✓	✓

3.7.3.1 Technical 'on-farm' Solutions

- **Mechanical Weeding:** Mechanical weeding plays a pivotal role for IWM in Spain. It includes innovative techniques like inter-row mechanical weeding, often integrated with precision farming technologies. This approach more popularly combines inter-row cultivation with camera-guided tools, but still face challenges as difficulty of purchase equipment, carbon footprint and need of training/technical services.
- **Targeted Herbicides:** While reducing herbicide use is a priority, targeted herbicide application is still a valuable component of IWM for farmers in Spain. Advanced technologies enable farmers to apply herbicides with precision, also allowing the combination with other techniques.
- **Cultural Control:** Cultural control methods, such as crop rotation, cover cropping, and altering planting densities, are employed to disrupt weed growth cycles and enhance crop competitiveness.
- **Mulching with wood chips and herbs:** Mulching using materials like wood chips and natural herbs acts as a protective barrier against weed growth. It can improve the results of other techniques by applying as a complementary method.
- **Silvopastoral methods:** The integration of livestock and poultry into vineyards and orchards, contributes to weed management and pest management. Grazing animals can selectively consume weeds, reducing their prevalence in the field.
- **Variety selection:** Choosing crop varieties that are naturally more competitive with weeds is an integral part of IWM. Varieties must be selected according with climatic conditions and crop complementary.
- **Robotics:** Emerging technologies like agricultural robotics are gaining prominence in weed management. Robotic systems can autonomously identify and remove weeds, reducing labour costs and herbicide usage but need for advisory services providing training and testing prior to purchasing.
- **Bioherbicides (Essential Oils):** Bioherbicides, derived from essential oils and other natural compounds, are increasingly being explored as eco-friendly alternatives to chemical herbicides. These substances offer targeted weed control while minimizing environmental impacts as demonstrated within the CONTECAD OG.

3.7.3.2 Policy support

- **Subsidies for Environmentally Friendly Farming:** One of the foremost political solutions is the provision of subsidies and incentives for environmentally friendly farming practices. By offering financial support to farmers who adopt IWM strategies in Spain, policy makers can motivate the agricultural sector to transition towards more sustainable and eco-conscious approaches to weed management.
- **Increase the Number of Grants for Farmer's Equipment:** Access to modern equipment and technology is essential for effective IWM in Spain. Increasing the number of grants available to farmers for the acquisition of specialized equipment designed for IWM, such as precision weeding tools and robotics, can significantly enhance the implementation of these practices.
- **Improving Advisory Services on IWM Practices:** Adequate knowledge and guidance are crucial for successful IWM implementation. Enhancing Spanish advisory services by training and deploying experts in IWM can help farmers make informed decisions and optimize their weed control strategies. Improved advisory services can bridge the gap between research findings and practical application in the field.
- **Grants for Trials of Alternative Methods:** To encourage experimentation and innovation in weed management, offering grants for trials of alternative methods is imperative. This financial support enables farmers to test and adapt emerging IWM practices, ensuring that they are both effective and tailored to local conditions.
- **Demonstration Events of Alternative Methods and Access to Information:** Hosting demonstration events and providing easy access to information on IWM practices are essential political solutions. These initiatives can showcase the benefits and feasibility of alternative weed control methods. By offering knowledge-sharing platforms, farmers can learn from one another's experiences and best practices, accelerating the adoption of IWM.

3.7.4 Conclusions for Spain

The supported discussion on alternative weed management practices in Spain underscores the readiness of Spanish farmers towards adopting sustainable weed control practices in agriculture. Thus, Spanish farmers are keen to adopt IWM practices to reduce the environmental and health risks associated with traditional herbicides while also improving cost-efficiency. Considering the Spanish OG CONTECAD and the responses to the D2.1 survey, horticultural crops, vineyards and arable crops have been considered as main cropping systems.

Key IWM strategies explored in Spain include mechanical weeding, targeted herbicides, cultural controls, mulching, silvopastoral methods, variety selection, robotics, and bioherbicides. These methods offer diverse options for effective weed management while minimizing negative impacts.

Furthermore, political solutions, such as subsidies, equipment grants, advisory services improvement, trial grants, and knowledge-sharing initiatives, play a crucial role in promoting IWM adoption. These policies support the transition to more sustainable agricultural practices in Spain.

Part. 4 Document Summary

The NAP for each participating country has been outlined in this report and now form the basis of the next WP (WP3) where they will be evaluated by the National Experts and relevant stakeholders.

The number of solutions selected varied between countries with a range of 10-20 solutions each. These solutions were taken from D2.1 and D2.2, so were country specific and then matched to the selected focus crops for each country. It was decided that individual countries could have up to three crops, but it depended on their original OG crop and the cropping system of the majority of survey respondents. Technical solutions were very diverse between countries but the general themes of; alternative weeding techniques such as different forms of mechanical weeding, precision or spot spraying, robots, thermal weeding, living mulches, cover crops and cultural options such as cultivar choice and crop rotations all

featured highly across Europe and the UK. Along with these technical solutions the NAP includes policy-based solutions that will require implementation to ensure the best uptake of Integrated weed management (IWM). These are aspects such as subsidies for equipment or independent efficacy trials, sustainable farming incentives and funded demonstration events, all of which are currently considered barriers to uptake.

It is important to consider that for some countries there are very large regional differences that may include climatic variation, soil type and predominant cropping systems. This would be the case for Italy, Spain and Greece in particular. For the purposes of this draft NAP we have not ventured into regional differences within a country, but that can be included in the next phase of NAP development in WP3. This information is critical to tailor 'Best Practices' designed to cater to the diverse needs, contexts, and farmer profiles found throughout Europe and the UK, which will be accomplished within the next phase of the project (WP3).

